

Vision based robot-to-robot object handover

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Abstract—This work deals with an autonomous robot-to-robot object handover in the presence of uncertainties. Both the giver and receiver robots are equipped with an hand-in-eye depth camera and a deep learning based approach is adopted for detecting the presence of the object. The physical exchange is performed by recurring to an estimate of the contact forces and an impedance control, which allows the receiver robot to perceive the presence of the object and the giver one to recognize that the handover is complete.

I. INTRODUCTION

Object handover is a typical industrial task involving robots cooperating with humans and/or with other robots (see Fig. 1) in quasi-autonomous production plants [1]. The task can be divided in two phases, namely the pre-handover and the physical exchange phase.

The pre-handover phase includes the object detection, in which the giver must recognize the presence of the object to hand over in its workspace, the object grasping, the transportation and the synchronization, i.e., finding an agreement about the exchange location and timing [2].

The physical exchange phase starts at the instant of the first contact between the receiver robot and the object grasped by the giver robot and ends when the giver fully releases the object to the receiver [1]. The physical exchange requires cooperation among the giver and receiver robots, thus vision and force feedback can be adopted for the giver in order to understand if the receiver has grasped the object. Only when the grasping is safe the giver can start to release the object and allow the transition to the receiver.

II. PROPOSED STRATEGY

The setup consists of two collaborative robot manipulators Franka Emika Panda, both equipped with a camera in eye-in-hand configuration. The camera on the giver robot is an Intel Realsense D435, while that mounted on the receiver robot is an Intel Realsense L515. The manipulated objects are a couple of counter-rotating shafts of different length and shape. It is assumed that the objects are placed in a box roughly positioned in the field of view of the giver’s camera. Due to the position uncertainties, the robot motion cannot be offline planned and the vision system is adopted in order to detect the presence, identify the class, and compute the pose of the objects. The complete pipeline for our approach is shown in Fig. 2 and detailed in the rest of this section.

A. Shaft detection

When the box containing the objects is completely in the camera field of view of the giver robot, a CNN detects the presence, the orientation and the type of the shafts.

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Fig. 1. Object handover between two robots. In this example, two Panda Emika Franka robots equipped with depth cameras are used for handing over a shaft.

To carry out the shaft detector, two CNN-based approaches, namely Faster R-CNN and YOLOv4, have been investigated to compare their performance and select the best architecture. Three object classes have been defined, namely

- Counter-rotating shaft exhaust (CSE);
- Counter-rotating shaft intake (CSI);
- Roller bearing (RB).

Detecting CSE and CSI is useful to identify the shaft’s type, while RB is used to determine the shaft axes and estimate the grasping point. A dataset made of 342 images of size 640×480 and split in two non-overlapping sets, namely the training (245 images) and test (97 images) sets, has been built by considering the two shafts, captured at different distances and with different orientation and background. A data augmentation step, using horizontal flipping and cropping operations, has been carried out to create a larger training set of 980 images.

To evaluate the detection performance, the mean average precision (mAP) metric has been considered [3]. The Average Precision (AP) for each class represents the integral of the precision-recall curve, measured for a certain value of the Intersection over Union (IoU). The Intersection over Union measures the overlap between the predicted bounding box and the labelled one. The mAP is the AP averaged over all classes.

Table I shows detection results on the test set for a value of IoU of 0.5. On the basis of these results and performance, the YOLOv4 architecture has been chosen to implement the shaft detector.

TABLE I
 AVERAGE PRECISION FOR IOU VALUE OF 0.5

Network Architecture	CSE	CSI	RB	mAP
YOLOv4	0.952	0.966	1.000	0.973
Faster R-CNN	0.928	0.855	1.000	0.914

B. Estimation of the grasping point

Once the shaft has been detected in the image, it is necessary to compute the position of the grasping point and the shaft orientation, which is crucial to compute the gripper orientation.

Fig. 2. Proposed pipeline. 1) Object detection phase. 2) Estimation of the grasping point. 3) Object grasping and motion to the exchange point. 4) Detection of the giver at the exchange position. 5) Object grasped by the receiver. 6) Object released by the giver.

It is assumed that, for both the shafts, a suitable grasping point should be located along the longitudinal axis. A two step procedure is used to estimate the position of the grasping points:

- 1) the shaft axis is estimated by connecting the centers of the two RB bounding boxes;
- 2) the grasping point is computed along this axis.

It is worth noticing that, due to possible variations in the detected bounding boxes size, the grasping point estimation could not be perfect. However, such uncertainties are managed in the physical exchange phase by ensuring a suitable compliance to the robots.

C. Shaft handover

Once the grasping point position and the shaft orientation have been detected, the giver robot can be commanded to grasp the shaft and move it to the exchange point. The exchange point is off-line determined on the basis of the work-cell configuration in such a way that the giver's gripper is in the field of view of the receiver's camera.

It is important to observe that the planned point is related to the end-effector reference frame, while the shaft tip position is unknown, due to the uncertainties of the grasping point estimation and the different length of the two shafts. Moreover, due to the absence of communications, the exchange point is unknown to the receiver, thus its motion cannot be planned off-line and performed via a pure positional control.

D. Object detected by the receiver

The receiver needs an exteroceptive sensor to detect the presence of the shaft and to align its gripper to the shaft axis. To this aim, it is equipped with a Intel Realsense L515 camera, while a marker is positioned on the giver robot. Thanks to the visual feedback, the receiver aligns its approach axis with the shaft axis and moves until a contact is detected. Since wrist mounted force-torque sensors are not present on the Franka Emika Panda robots, the contact detection is provided by a momentum-based observer [4]. The receiver detects the first contact with the shaft when the estimated force along the shaft axis overcomes a suitable threshold and then closes the gripper.

E. Physical exchange phase

During the physical exchange phase, different behaviors for the giver and the receiver are required. When the receiver

hits the object, a force along the shaft axis is exchanged by the robots. In order to successfully perform the handover, in this phase the giver has to keep constant its position and orientation (which is crucial to make possible the grasping of the receiver), while the receiver must be enough compliant to avoid large contact forces and mechanical stresses on the shaft. The receiver detects the first contact with the shaft when the estimated force along the shaft axis overcomes a threshold. Then, it closes the gripper and starts to move upward, while the giver has to be controlled to compliantly follow the receiver motion. During the motion, a force along the shaft axis is experienced on the giver's end-effector, and, when its magnitude reaches a certain threshold, the giver opens the gripper and the object is fully released to the receiver. To enforce the desired behaviors to the robots, an admittance control [5] has been implemented. Moreover, to impose a leader-following behavior during the exchange, a different virtual stiffness has been set to the robots depending on the force direction.

III. RESULTS

Experimental results show that a combination of learning and visual approaches, together with a compliant control strategy, allows to achieve an autonomous execution of a complex industrial task in a partially structured environment. Moreover, the effectiveness of the approach has been proven in the absence of explicit communication among the robots and of force/torque sensors.

A video demonstration of the proposed method is available on this link <http://www2.unibas.it/automatica/multimedia.html>

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